

A legal system for urbanism: the Modern Movement's unseen face

The CIAMs, urbanism and urban legislation

An analysis of the texts produced by architects identified with the Modern Movement reveals that legislation was a fundamental issue, and that their propositions reached far beyond the Athens Charter and so-called functional zoning. The subsequent development of a sound understanding of urban legislation hinged on questioning the regulatory system based on hygienist urbanism which prevailed in the twenties, notably in France and Germany.

The Modern Movement criticized several aspects of the hygienic model of legislation, including its affirmation of the traditional family as expressed in low-rise, unicellular dwellings with private gardens; its disregard for the potentialities of vertical collective housing, such as free spaces and community-shared facilities; its hypocrisy, as manifested in unhygienic, poorly insulated and ventilated dwellings designed to answer to speculative interests; its rigidity and inadequacy in responding to the population's economic circumstances; and finally, its dismissal of users and professional entities as participants in the development and implementation of laws.

The recurrence of the legislation theme at the CIAMs meetings signals the importance of urbanism in the perspective of the Modern Movement, since the quest for legislation broached not only questions related to the forms of buildings but also to their urban insertion and to the town's spatial order as a whole. The constant effort to establish a close architecture-urbanism dialogue reflects the

consensus amongst modernist architects that the issue of modern life encompasses urban living. In this respect, according to Gold (1997: 16), it is in the city and by means of the city that the challenges of modernity are to be found.

Therefore, radical changes in the legislative approach were seen as intrinsic to finding a solution to the problem of designing a minimum living space within a framework of vertical construction, which featured good lighting, free and flexible design, green outdoor spaces, standardisation, rationalisation and economy, the use of new construction methods demanded by the industrial era, while still preserving the concepts of the housing unit, of the neighbourhood, and of the city in its totality.

The Preparatory International Congress on Modern Architecture held in 1928 at La Sarraz (France) - later known as the CIAM I-, already included urbanism as one of the topics for discussion, relating it to other issues - standardisation and rationalisation in construction, and the relationship between architecture and economic order. In the Congress' final declaration, urbanism was defined as the organisation of functions in collective life, involving town and country. Three key urban functions - shelter, work and leisure-, were to be articulated by a fourth function: circulation. In order to make these principles effective, mechanisms such as control over land-use, legislation and regulation of traffic are outlined.

It was at this first meeting that the idea of land redistribution and the end of private property emerged, as well as its less radical formulation, which called for the abolition of the chaotic partition of land through sale, speculation and inheritance by redistributing between landowners and community the unearned increment resulting from works of joint interest. (Gold,op.cit.: 59)

In subsequent meetings, the understanding of the relationship between housing and the city acquired more and more complexity. CIAM II, held in Frankfurt am Main in 1929, with the theme "Housing for lower income groups and the notion of the minimum dwelling", can be understood as the moment in which that relationship was first emphasised at the level of the neighbourhood. Public facilities - nurseries, sports areas, refectories and laundries -, were incorporated in the concept of habitation. To resolve and organise those and other urban spaces, vertical construction and increased population density were introduced as key elements.

Two papers directly broached the subject of urban legislation: "Sociological fundamentals of minimum dwelling", by Walter Gropius, and "Building codes and minimum dwelling", by Hans Schmidt.¹

The debate on legislation emphasised, on the one hand the need for laws adequate to new materials,

new construction systems and new ways of life. On the other hand, legislation was viewed as the state's instrument of intervention to assure housing quality and protection from speculative interests, in order to develop potentially low-cost housing for workers, and to control tenancy rent. Legislation must also be flexible, involve the participation of different professionals in its implementation, and address both construction and urban planning. This set of issues would direct the debates on legislation at later meetings.

At CIAM III in Brussels 1930, where the theme was "Low cost housing and rational site planning", concerns moved from the scale of the neighbourhood to that of the town. The same biological reasons that influenced the determination of minimum dwelling – space, air, light and heat, essential for the full development of mankind's vital functions —, were transferred to and deemed decisive on the scale of urban planning. One could say the assumptions for the discussion of the Functional City in CIAM IV were established at the meeting in Brussels. The *Ville Radieuse* scheme was presented for the first time by Le Corbusier in Brussels. Le Corbusier's plan featured standard housing units organised in blocks, with separate circulation for vehicles and pedestrians. Other propositions of urban organisation, mostly by German architects, were grounded on the same principles, and aimed towards the creation of a healthy, green town with orderly traffic.

Parallel to the rise of urbanism as an area of concern; legislation became more and more widely an object of consideration, and was more emphatically viewed as an indispensable element to put into effect the proposals. This can be observed in the introduction to the CIAM III minutes by Gideon and in two papers on the problem of urban legislation, "Low-rise, medium height and high-rise buildings" by Gropius, and "The partition of land in cities", by Le Corbusier.²

In his essay, Gideon pointed to the rigid and retrogressive aspects of urban legislation and to the need for improved flexibility as fundamental to solving the housing problem. For Le Corbusier, the central concern was the opposition between the dispersed city – the garden cities—and the concentrated cities, vertically constructed. Beyond simply raising the issue for discussion, the Congress sought to change municipal laws in many towns and cities in the world. The modernist proposals, according to the architects, could not be accomplished with partial changes; instead, they demanded a whole new set of rules, starting from redistribution of the land. Redistribution was seen as the "only pathway to urbanism", since property is subdivided, its inalienable character condemns "all attempts to col-

lective betterment". Therefore, along with an urban system adequate to the machines era, new laws must effect what Le Corbusier called "the true revolution in the sacred notion of property": the re-arrangement of the partitioned land. This was a pre-condition to ensuring the collective attainment embodied spatially by vertical buildings, wide open spaces, suppression of patios and passages, "pilotis" and roof-gardens. (Le Corbusier, 1930: 233-242)

In considering the proper spatial organisation of the large city, CIAM members believed that vertical housing had the advantage of precluding large commuting distances and consequently would save time and resources used in locomotion. It would also allow for the creation of large public green areas, which they considered more viable than the private gardens linked to unicellular dwellings. Gropius reinforced his 1929 theory that instead of restricting building heights, population density limits ought to be applied. Correct orientation in terms of sun and site would ensure better insulation as well as lower urbanisation costs and provide quieter roads, by allowing for lower-circulation routes and pedestrian precincts. CIAM argued for zoning legislation for the whole town, to promote that urban condition.

CIAM IV, structured around the theme "Functional City I (Analysis)", was the decisive moment in terms of modern architects focus on urban issues, with the presentation and discussion of 33 city plans elaborated by 17 international groups. CIAM IV established a course that would be followed until CIAM VII—namely, the attempt by architects—to expand their field of action to the realm of urbanism. Although the conclusions reached by the Congress were never published due to lack of consensus, the two most accessible documents — Le Corbusier's 1941 "Athens Charter", and "Can our cities survive?", assembled and edited by José Luís Sert (1942), both attempted to legitimize architects' claims for participation in city planning, and in the design of neighbourhood units and expressway systems. (Gold, op.cit)

The Athens Charter repeatedly referred to legislation as an instrument for improving modern housing. Not only did the Charter encompass the repertoire of modern architecture, but it also incorporated urban solutions already being implemented in the large cities of Europe and America. In the Athens Charter, Le Corbusier (1941) again emphasised the urgent need to establish rules to dispose by legal means of usable land, essential to balance harmoniously the vital needs of the individual with the collective. To that end, he proposed the creation of the "land statute" to regulate the balance between built and unbuilt areas, thus demarcating green areas, systems and facilities for all residential

districts. The Charter also reinforced zoning as an instrument for ordering urban space, taking into consideration the four basic urban functions.

In his essay, Sert (1942) focused on legislation as one of the obstacles the urban expert was likely to confront; to overcome this obstacle, he should associate with other experts, such as legislators and economists. Comprehensive planning would require land acquisition as well as specific legislation to enable national and regional enforcement.

If one reflects upon the themes of the meetings before CIAM IX, (after which revisions of concepts and a leadership crisis took place), it is noticeable that they were all linked to the great directives consolidated in the CIAM IV. At the 1937 CIAM V meeting in Paris, the theme was Functional City II (Housing and Leisure), while at the 1947 CIAM VI in Bridgewater, the discussion on planning at multiple scales prompted two new fields of action—national and regional planning. Two years later, during the CIAM VII meeting at Bergamo, Le Corbusier presented the CIAM Grid, consisting of a methodological proposal for developmental analysis of cities in different scales, functions and contexts. At Hoddeston in 1951, the theme was “The heart of the town”.

The prevalence of urban concepts demonstrates the extent to which the legislative principles established in the Athens Charter were adopted after CIAM IV. The discussion stimulated by Schmidt, although partly incorporated in the architects’ discourse was never fully adopted. Instead of viewing urban legislation as an instrument for the control and assurance of rights, the law was seen as a means for realizing modern urban and architectonic principles. In other words—legislation continued to be understood as just a rationalised technique for the ordering of space

Hans Schmidt: urban legislation as an instrument of control and assurance of rights

The German architect Hans Schmidt contributed, in 1929, the most innovative text on urban legislation to be presented at the CIAM meetings. Some of the issues raised by Schmidt are relevant in the current debate on urban legislation in Brazil. In “Building codes and minimum dwelling,” Schmidt argues for conceiving of legislation not only as a rationalised technique to order space, but also as an instrument of control and assurance of rights involving the state, user and professionals.

While the majority of discussions on legislation at the CIAM meetings were generally concerned with strategies for making architectonic solutions and their insertion in urban space possible, Hans Schmidt dealt not only with technical issues but also with the

social and economic aspects of legislative reform. Consideration of these aspects required a redefinition of the relationships between the state and other actors engaged in the construction of towns. Furthermore, Schmidt gave primacy to the role of architects and their associations, evidently with the intention of displacing the influence of doctors and engineers in urban legislation.

Schmidt indicated above all the need for distinguishing two levels of legislation: the urban level and that of construction and habitability; the former concerned the limits of individuals in their mutual rapport, and the latter of the individual towards the community, which must, by means of technical criteria, assure a given degree of quality in construction.

Second, Schmidt designated flexibility in legislation as essential, and pointed out that, with the exception of laws limiting property rights, all rules concerning construction must be passed in the form of codes. Whereas the technical criteria related to social and hygienic issues should be general norms, those regulating stability and fire prevention, must be precise rules implemented and enforced by means of updated scientific methods. But in both instances, flexibility must be assured for defining housing programmes and fulfilling social and hygienic needs, as well as for selecting materials and construction systems.

Schmidt discussed a third aspect, the role of the state, which he said must be limited to that necessary to produce quality control. According to Schmidt, from the moment construction turns into the speculative production of goods, criteria become essential. If the state sponsors a free market in which virtually anyone is allowed to establish himself as a builder of residences, it is the same state’s responsibility to protect tenants against losses resulting from the actions of irresponsible and unqualified builders.

However, to guarantee the quality of housing, Schmidt claimed that some measure of state regulation over the economy was necessary. In other words, laws must consider innovations in construction methods and hygienic requirements, as well as new ways of living proposed by architects, while always keeping economic circumstances in mind. The standard of ideal housing imposed by a strictly legalist view had not shown itself to be economically viable in post-war times. Consequently, less expensive housing forms started to materialise without a proper legislation to follow suit. Making a decision on housing quality for the poorer population always comes down to the inevitable dilemma of calculating production costs versus feasible rent.

Fourthly, Schmidt argued for the inclusion of professional entities in the process of creating and enacting laws, in other words, removing law-making

from the exclusive domain of the state. He believed that professional associations of architects and engineers should be consulted on the formulation and revision of laws, and also participate in their elaboration and application.

Lastly, Schmidt emphasized the importance of laws for upholding the technical and social responsibility of producers: construction must be organised in communities, guilds and public interest bases. He outlined the role of architects and the nature of their interventions in production: architects must introduce new ideas in the production of habitation and try to re-establish direct communication between user and builder. Instead of allowing themselves to be guided strictly by laws, architects must seek the collaboration of science, industry and users, to originate and advance knowledge.

For Schmidt, it was also part of the architect's mandate to challenge the speculative construction of dwellings, and to free housing from the influence of a-social regulating forces. As responsible specialists, architects should proactively advance changes in methods and deeds, rather than trust that better habitation conditions will come about through the force of norms. The first step in that direction was to guarantee that the construction of dwellings be executed by skilled and reliable professionals who possessed the necessary experience.

Schmidt's formulation positioned urban legislation as part of the legal system that permeated and structured society, and provided a basic element of predictability and stability in social relations. In other words, Schmidt's modernist perception of legislation was not limited to a set of norms; it took into account not only the passing of laws but also modes of application, public character, independence from the judiciary, etc.

Brasília – legislation as a rationalised technique towards a sole project

Formulated soon after Brasília's inauguration, the legislation governing the capital city revealed the limits of the modern architects' urban vision as it was conceived in the 1930s and 40s. The legislation also reflected the importance of Le Corbusier's Athens Charter document in diffusing modernist notions of the city in Brazil.

If there is one aspect that substantiates Brasília as a veritable CIAM city, it is Lucio Costa's radical dialogue between architecture and urbanism. By introducing himself "not as a fully prepared technician" but as a "mere *maquis* (guerrilla fighter) for urbanism", Costa (1956) clearly wanted to occupy the space claimed by architects in urban planning.

In the remaining aspects, Brasília can be defined as a Corbusian city, a straightforward translation of

the principles of spatial organisation set forth in the Athens Charter, which since the early thirties had been gradually introduced in the new town projects and in the urban legislation of a significant number of towns in Brazil

In the thirties and thereafter, layouts of new towns contained a superimposition of the Athens Charter principles over those of Ebenezer Howard's Garden City. The influence of Garden City precepts could be seen in the sinuous and irregular design of residential developments, large green wooded areas and collective facilities. From the Athens Charter they extracted functional zoning and land use parameters which favored free-standing objects, detached from any boundary conditions, such as Atilio Correia Lima's Goiânia plan, Jorge Macedo Vieira's Maringá, Águas de São Pedro and Cianorte, and others.

The Garden City principles had been gradually incorporated into Brazilian towns since the first decade of the twentieth century. In contrast, the adoption of Athens Charter precepts, was paced by the release, mostly by architects' entities, of CIAM discussions being held. The perception of zoning grounded on mankind's four basic functions became emblematic of modernist notions adopted.

The progressive absorption of modernist postulates becomes evident when we analyze new towns and their corresponding urban legislation between 1933 and 1960, from the Goiânia project to the legislation on Brasília. In his report on the Goiânia project, Corrêa Lima wrote that "the town zoning seeks to follow modern tendencies", and stressed the importance of zonal regulations. Goiânia's first Building Ordinances (1937) delineated zones and anticipated their observance. The same applies to the Águas de São Pedro (1938) and Londrina (1951) codes and the Maringá project (1947) and building ordinances (1959). Even rectangular, geometric Panorama, which was designed by Prestes Maia in 1952 along the model of the City Beautiful Movement, followed a self-imposed zonal regime.³

The diffusion of comprehensive zoning reached to the Brazilian capitals, and in 1936 and 1937 Recife and Rio respectively incorporated zonal regulations by function to their building ordinances. In the forties and fifties zoning laws were increasingly adopted in a great number of Brazilian cities. In the cities, unlike newly planned towns where legislation was expected to preserve the principles established by the project, legislation aimed at changing the existing physical context by imposing a new rationality on the urban space. The new model was imposed in order to organise and distribute urban functions, review dimensions of lots and relocate the construction within lots.

Beginning in the thirties, these new regulating principles marked a change in urban practices, with mounting consequence for legislation as a planning instrument, offsetting to some extent the importance of plans. Comprehensive zoning gained ascendancy as a privileged strategy for the control of urban space. It was mainly based on the American urbanism of the twenties, and the Athens Charter constituted the second source that provided and consolidated its diffusion in Brasil.⁴

Decree # 7 of June 12, 1960 passing the Brasília legislation rendered in pure form the Athens Charter's principles on spatial organisation. Compared to the zoning laws at the time the Brasília legislation was notably radical in its regulation and specificity of functional separation, construction and materials typologies, as well as the definition of formal attributes of the buildings.

Brasília was governed by a functional zoning system which rigidly divided the city into seven mono-functional sectors: administrative sectors (the three-powers square, the promenade of ministries, government agencies and the area reserved for the municipal centre); commercial sectors (local and central trade, south-and-north banking, south-and-north lodging and entertainment); mixed uses building sector (commercial and residential); industrial sectors (supplies and storage industries, supplies centre, publishing industries); special purposes building sector (large area sector, filling stations, wash and lubrication stations, fuelling stations, schools, cinemas, theatres, hospitals; embassies and legations sector; and three kinds of residential sectors, differentiated according to typology: detached, semi-detached and collective (superblocks). (Art. 2, chapter II)

For each housing typology definitions of standard measurements, clearance and land occupation were provided. For collective housing highly detailed recommendations were specified, down to the materials to enclose laundry and service areas, and distances between axes for columns. The same level of detail existed in regulations for commercial and industrial construction.

A full chapter of the law was dedicated to the formal aspects of building, restricting repetition in the design of "public" or "sizeable" buildings, requiring that "their origin may be identifiable" (art. 54). Peculiar or special architectural designs were only permitted outside the urbanised zones, provided their land occupation does not exceed 1/4 of the plot. The planning sector of city administration was granted the right to "restrain exotic, disproportionate or ridiculous designs that may jeopardise the architectural quality of the capital city", as well as to have the final word on external finishing materials (art. 55). Buildings in the Supplies and Stor-

age Sectors and Supply Centre were to conform to the architectural design and standards elaborated by the planning sector (art. 60).

If the Brasília legislation is analysed against the background of the CIAM principles, particularly those pointed out by Schmidt, it is clear that the law did not intend any redefinition of the relationship between the state and other actors involved in the construction of towns. In fact, it was a legislation formulated to render viable a single, monolithic project, and even more than that, a finished, fixed project. Its formulation did not allow for the urban dynamics and mutability of living circumstances, considerations which inspired the founding of the CIAM meetings and steered their discussions and propositions. Quite the contrary, the Brasília legislation ossified Lucio Costa's project by not admitting changes or urban expansion. By conceiving the law as an instrument that congeals an urban situation, it subverted all of the postulates about legislation introduced at the CIAM meetings which aimed at radically changing the great urban centres.

In place of flexible legislation—granting housing programmes freedom to fulfill social and hygienic requirements, and to select constructive materials and systems, a whole set of rules restricted users, builders and architects like a straitjacket. For the architect, instead of innovating housing production, encouraging the co-operation of science, industry and users, and advancing the relationship between user and producer, all that was left was submission to the law. The state, formerly limited to product quality control, became an aesthetic censor and project formulator.

Concerning the question of economic housing, Costa (op.cit.) assigned to the Companhia Urbanizadora the responsibility "to provide within the proposed arrangement for decent and economic accommodation for the totality of the population", and recommended "preventing the encystation of shanty towns both in the urban and rural peripheries". Whereas Costa stated that the plan sought "a certain degree of social coexistence, thus preventing undue and undesirable stratification", in Decree n.7 a specific area for "economic housing" was established, distant and segregated from the main design. In contrast to the rigidity present in the recommendations for other typologies, the law did not provide in any way rules for the construction of this kind of housing.

In fact, altogether ignored both in the plan and the law was any discussion concerning the state's, producers' and particularly architects' technical and social responsibility, to ensure accessible and quality housing for the working population.

It is clear that the 1960 law on Brasília was out of step with the political and social dimensions of the

legal system implicit in the CIAM theses. The same, however, is not true of Brasília's legislation in relation to the urban practices at the time in Brazil: Brasília's legislation reaffirmed the existing legal system and did not break with two essential aspects of creation of urban legislation consolidated in the forties and fifties - a strictly technical product imposed by means of decrees.

NOTES

¹ Ernst May, Le Corbusier, and Victor Bourgeois also presented works at CIAM II.

² Other works were presented by Boehm and Kaufmann, Richard J. Neutra, and K. Teige.

³ Prestes Maia's proposed zonal regime is part of the technical memorandum accompanying the city plan. His notes were not passed as town legislation.

⁴ On American influence in the construction of zoning in Brazil and decline in the importance of plan, see Feldman (1997)

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KEYWORDS

legislation, urbanism, Modern Movement, Brasilia.

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